

STUDY OF EXTENDED Φ -CONTRACTION MAPPINGS IN PROBABILISTIC METRIC SPACE

Radha¹, Arvind Bhatt^{2*} and Deepak Kumar Sharma³

^{1,2}Department of Mathematics, School of Sciences, Uttarakhand Open University Haldwani, Nainital, Uttarakhand, India

³Department of Mathematics, MBPG College, Kumaun University, Nainital
radhajoshi321@gmail.com¹, arvindbhatt@uou.ac.in^{2*} and sharmadeepak0111209@gmail.com³

ABSTRACT

We extend the concept of Φ -contraction mappings in the probabilistic metric space.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The main object of Fixed-point theory is solving the non – linear equations of the type $Tx = x$, in which the function T is defined on some abstract space X . The amazing Banach Contraction principle [1] is widely recognised as one of the most important and practical findings in contemporary mathematical analysis. It offers a useful technique for locating those fixed points and ensures the presence and uniqueness property of fixed points for specific self – maps in a whole metric space.

In 1968 Kannan [14] proved that there are maps with fixed points and discontinuity in their domain after that Meir and Keeler [16] obtained the unique fixed point for new contractive condition. In continuation of many researchers finds the fixed point and unique fixed points for different type of mappings (Boyd and Wong [6], Matkowski [15], Rhoades [34], Jungck et al. [13], Jachymski [12], R.P. Pant [19-32], Pasicki [34], Reich [35], V. Pant [30], Bhatt et al.[3] Bisht and Pant [4], Bisht and Rakocevic [5]).

Our main aim in this research paper the study of contraction criterion in the probabilistic metric space which was given by Boyd and Wong [6]. Menger [17] proposed the theory of probabilistic metric spaces in relation in physics. Sehgal [38, 39] made the first attempt in this area by starting the research of contraction mapping theorems in probabilistic metric spaces in his doctoral dissertation. Since then, a significant advancement in the development of fixed-point theorems in Mangar space [8, 9, 18] has been made by Sehgal and Bharucha-Reid [2] who obtained a generalization of the Banach Contraction Principle on a complete Menger space.

In this research paper we are finding the results in probabilistic metric space.

2. MATHEMATICAL PRELIMINARIES

Definition 2.1. [37, 38]. A distribution function (on $[-\infty, +\infty)$) is a function $F: [-\infty, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ which is left-continuous on \mathbb{R} , non-decreasing and $F(-\infty) = 0, F(+\infty) = 1$. The Heaviside function H is a distribution function defined by,

$$H(t) = \begin{cases} 0, & \text{if } t \leq 0 \\ 1, & \text{if } t > 0. \end{cases}$$

Definition 2.2. [10]. A distance distribution function $F: [-\infty, +\infty) \rightarrow [0, 1]$ is distribution function with support contained in $[0, \infty)$. The family of all distance distribution functions will be denoted by Δ^+ . We denote

$$D^+ = \left\{ F: F \in \Delta^+, \lim_{x \rightarrow \infty} F(x) = 1 \right\}.$$

Stochastic Modelling and Computational Sciences

Definition 2.3. [36, 37]. A probabilistic metric space in the sense of Schweizer and Sklar is an ordered pair (X, F) , where X is a nonempty set and $F : X \times X \rightarrow \Delta^+$ if and only if the following conditions are satisfied ($F(x, y) = F_{x,y}$ for every $x, y \in X \times X$):

- (i) for every $(x, y) \in X \times X, F_{x,y}(0) = 0$;
- (ii) for every $(x, y) \in X \times X, F_{x,y} = F_{y,x}$;
- (iii) $F_{x,y} = 1$, for every $t > 0 \iff x = y$;
- (iv) for every $(x, y, z) \in X \times X \times X$ and for every $t_1, t_2 > 0$,
 $F_{x,y}(t_1) = 1, F_{y,z}(t_2) = 1, \implies F_{x,z}(t_1 + t_2) = 1$.

For each x and y in X and for each real number $t \geq 0, F_{x,y}(t)$ is to be thought of as the probability that the distance between x and y is less than t . Indeed, if (X, d) is a metric space, then the distribution function $F_{x,y}(t)$ defined by the relation $F_{x,y}(t) = H(t - d(x, y))$ induces a probabilistic metric space.

Definition 2.6 [10]. A t -norm is a function $T: [0, 1] \times [0, 1] \rightarrow [0, 1]$ satisfying the following conditions:

- (i) $T(a, 1) = a, T(0, 0) = 0$
- (ii) $T(a, b) = T(b, a)$
- (iii) $T(c, d) \geq T(a, b)$ for $c \geq a, d \geq b$
- (iv) $T(T(a, b), c) = T(a, T(b, c))$ for all a, b, c in $[0, 1]$.

Definition 2.7 [10]. A Menger probabilistic metric space (X, F, T) is an ordered triad, where T is a t -norm, and (X, F) is probabilistic metric space satisfying the following condition:

$$F_{xz}(t_1 + t_2) \geq T(F_{xy}(t_1), F_{yz}(t_2)) \text{ for all } x, y, z \text{ in } X \text{ and } t_1, t_2 \geq 0.$$

Definition 2.8 [10]. Let (X, F) be a probabilistic metric space. The (ϵ, λ) -topology in (X, F) is generated by the family of neighbourhoods

$$U = \{(U_v(\epsilon, \lambda): (v, \epsilon, \lambda \in X \times R^+ \times (0, 1))\},$$

$$\text{Where } (U_v(\epsilon, \lambda) = \{u: u \in X, F_{u,v}(\epsilon) > 1 - \lambda\}.$$

If a t -norm T is such that $\sup_{x < 1} T(x, x) = 1$ then (X, F, T) is with the (ϵ, λ) topology, a metrizable topological space.

Definition 2.9 [10]. Let (X, F) be a probabilistic metric space. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in (X, F) is said to converge a point $x \in X$ if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda > 0$, there exists a positive integer $N(\epsilon, \lambda)$ such that

$$F_{x_n, x}(\epsilon) > 1 - \lambda \text{ for all } n \geq N(\epsilon, \lambda).$$

Definition 2.10 [10]. Let (X, F) be a probabilistic metric space. A sequence $\{x_n\}$ in (X, F) is said to be a Cauchy sequence point if for every $\epsilon > 0$ and $\lambda > 0$, there exists a positive integer $N(\epsilon, \lambda)$ such that

$$F_{x_n, x_m}(\epsilon) > 1 - \lambda \text{ for all } n, m \geq N(\epsilon, \lambda).$$

Stochastic Modelling and Computational Sciences

Definition 2.11 [10].A probabilistic metric space (X, F) with continuous t – norm is said to be complete if every Cauchy sequence in X converge to a point in X .

Definition 2.4 [7, 11]. If T is a self-mapping of a set X then a point x in X is called an eventually fixed point of T if there exists a natural number N such that

$$T^{n+1}(x) = T^n(x) \text{ for } n \geq N.$$

If $T(x) = x$ then x is called a fixed point of T . A point x in X is called a periodic point of period n if $T^n x = x$. The least positive integer n for which $T^n x = x$ is called the prime period of x .

Definition 2.5 [6,7] The set $\{x \in X : Tx = x\}$ is called the fixed point set of the mapping $T : X \rightarrow X$.

3. MAIN RESULTS

In this section we are finding the results in probabilistic metric space.

Theorem 3.1. Let (X, F) be a probabilistic metric space and $T : X \rightarrow X$ such that for each x, y in X with $x \neq Tx$ or $y \neq Ty$ we have

$$F_{Tx, Ty}(t) \geq \emptyset[F_x, y(t)] \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

Where $\emptyset : \mathbb{R}_+ \cup \{0\} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}_+ \cup \{0\}$ is such that $\emptyset(t) < t$ for $t > 0$. If T is upper semi continuous from the right or if \emptyset is non-decreasing and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \emptyset^n(t) = 0, t > 0$, then T has a fixed point. T has a unique fixed point \Leftrightarrow (i) is satisfied for each $x \neq y$ in X .

Proof. We can say when $x = Tx$ and $y = Ty$ and using (i), then

$$F_{Tx, Ty}(t) = [F_x, y(t)].$$

We can say that T is continuous and $F_{Tx, Ty}(t) \geq \emptyset[F_x, y(t)]$ for each x, y in X . Let y_0 be any point in X and $\{y_n\}$ be the sequence defined by

$$y_n = Ty_{n-1},$$

that is $y_n = T^n y_0$. If $y_{n+1} = y_n$ for some n , then y_n is a fixed point of T and theorem holds. Therefore, assume that $y_{n+1} \neq y_n$ for each $n \geq 0$.

Given an integer $p \geq 1$, let $k_n = F_{y_n, y_{n+p}}(t)$. Then using (i), for each $n \geq 1$ and $p \geq 1$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{We have } k_n &= F_{y_n, y_{n+p}}(t) \\ &= F_{Ty_{n-1}, Ty_{n+p-1}}(t) \\ &\geq \emptyset [F_{y_{n-1}, y_{n+p-1}}(t)] = \emptyset(k_{n-1}) \\ &\geq \emptyset^2 [F_{y_{n-2}, y_{n+p-2}}(t)] \geq \emptyset^2(k_{n-2}) \dots\dots\dots \geq \emptyset^n [F_{y_0, y_p}(t)] = \emptyset^n(k_0) \end{aligned}$$

Therefore $k_n \geq \emptyset^n(k_0)$.

Since $\{k_n\}$ is strictly increasing in \mathbb{R}_+ ,

there exist $L \leq 1$ such that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} k_n = L = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \emptyset(k_n). \tag{2}$$

Stochastic Modelling and Computational Sciences

Now assume that T satisfies Matkowski condition [10], that is, ϕ is nonincreasing and

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \phi^n(t) = 1 \text{ for each } t > 0.$$

Then, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} k_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \phi^n(k_0) = 1$.

This implies that $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

Next assume that T satisfies Boyd and Wond [6] condition, that is, ϕ is upper semi continuous from the right.

If $L < 1$ then we get

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} \sup \phi(k_n) \geq \phi(L) > L,$$

Which contradicts (2) since $k_n < L$.

Hence, $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} k_n = \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_{y_n, y_{n+p}}(t) = 1$ and $\{y_n\}$ is a Cauchy sequence.

Since X is complete, there exists z in X such that $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} y_n = z$ and $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ty_n = z$. Continuity of T implies $\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} Ty_n = Tz$, that is, $z = Tz$ and z is a fixed point of T.

Further, let u be any point in X.

Since $T^n y_0 \neq T^{n-1} y_0$ for each n, using (i) we get

$$\begin{aligned} F_{T^n u, T^n y_0}(t) &\geq \phi \left(F_{T^{n-1} u, T^{n-1} y_0}(t) \right) \\ &\geq \phi^2 \left(F_{T^{n-2} u, T^{n-2} y_0}(t) \right) \geq \dots \geq \phi^n \left(F_{u, y_0}(t) \right) \end{aligned}$$

Our assumption on ϕ imply that

$$\lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} F_{T^n u, T^n y_0}(t) = 0, \text{ that is, } \lim_{n \rightarrow \infty} T^n u = z.$$

Thus, if there exists a point y_0 such that

$$T^{n+1} y_0 \neq T^n y_0 \text{ for each } n,$$

then for each u in X the sequence of iterates $\{T^n u\}$ converges to z and z is the unique fixed point of T. Therefore, $T^{n+1} y_0 \neq T^n y_0, n \geq 0$, for some y_0 implies uniqueness of the fixed point.

Now, assume the condition (i) is satisfied for all x, y in X. Then T can have only one fixed point. Conversely, suppose that T has a unique fixed point.

Then for distinct x, y we have $x \neq fx$ or $y \neq fy$ which implies that condition (i) holds for each $x \neq y$ it may be noted that a mapping T satisfying this theorem cannot possess periodic point of prime period ≥ 2 .

If possible, suppose T satisfies Theorem 2.1 and x is periodic point of T with prime period 2, that is, $T^2 x = x$ but $Tx \neq x$.

Then using (1) we get

$$F_{Tx, T^2 y_0}(t) \geq \phi[F_{x, Ty}(t)] > F_{x, Ty}(t) = F_{T^2 x, Tx}(t).$$

This is a contradiction.

It follows similarly that T cannot have periodic points of prime period < 2 .

This completes the proof of the theorem.

Stochastic Modelling and Computational Sciences

Example 3.2. Let (X, F) be a probabilistic metric space, where $X = [1, \infty)$ and

$$F_{x,y}(t) = \begin{cases} e^{-\frac{|x-y|}{t}}, & \text{if } t > 0 \\ 0, & \text{if } t = 0 \end{cases}$$

Where $T: X \rightarrow X$ be a signum function $Tx = \text{sgn } x$ defined as

$$Tx = -1 \text{ if } x < 0, T0 = 0, Tx = 1 \text{ if } x > 0.$$

Then $Tx = 1$ for each x and 1 is the unique fixed point of T . T satisfies condition (i) with $\phi(t) = \frac{1}{2}t$. Here if $x \neq 1$ then $Tx = T^2x$ and x is an eventually fixed point.

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Stochastic Modelling and Computational Sciences

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